

STUDY OF RISK FACTORS FOR ADVERSE PERINATAL OUTCOMES IN WOMEN WITH PREECLAMPSIA.

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Introduction.

Hypertensive disorders during pregnancy are one of the most common causes of perinatal mortality. These disorders are closely related to many factors, which makes them difficult to predict and prevent. Early diagnosis and proper treatment play a crucial role in the well-being and life of a woman and her child [2].

Preeclampsia is a serious complication of pregnancy that develops after the 20th week of pregnancy. Preeclampsia occurs in 2-8% of pregnancies, is one of the most important causes of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality, and has no downward trend. Maternal mortality is 12 times higher when developing preeclampsia before 28 weeks of pregnancy. [4,6].

Preeclampsia has long-term consequences for both mother and her child. The danger of this complication is that it does not heal completely after the end of pregnancy [8].

The purpose of the study – to identify associations between preeclampsia management tactics and perinatal outcomes.

Materials and methods.

The independent variables were socio-demographic factors such as the age and place of residence of the patients; factors related to obstetrics; the duration of pregnancy (at the time of admission and delivery); prenatal monitoring of the current pregnancy; current medical history (concomitant diseases); condition at the time of admission, such as blood pressure measurement, proteinuria level, and also, signs and symptoms of target organ damage; treatment methods, including antihypertensive and anticonvulsant drugs, method of delivery; as well as other perinatal factors, such as fetal heartbeat during childbirth, Apgar score, and birth weight. The gestational age was considered reliable if it was calculated based on the last normal menstrual cycle or using obstetric ultrasound. The relationships were checked using Pearson's X²-criterion and binary logistic regression, with a p-value < 0.05 considered significant.

Results and Discussion.

In this study, almost 20 out of 100 newborns whose mothers suffered from preeclampsia died. This indicator was higher (76.59% versus 23.4%) among newborns whose mothers suffered from severe preeclampsia, compared with newborns whose mothers suffered from mild preeclampsia ($p = 0.01$). More than two thirds of the patients (69.3%) received magnesium sulfate to prevent seizures. Perinatal mortality among women with diastolic blood pressure above 110 mmHg at admission was almost 3 times higher (adjusted odds ratio (AOR) = 2.824; 95% confidence interval (CI) (1,154–6,038)) compared with women with diastolic blood pressure below 110 mmHg.

Conclusion.

Over the past 5 years, the perinatal mortality rate among women with preeclampsia who were in hospital treatment was extremely high, with the number of stillbirths exceeding the number of cases of early neonatal mortality before discharge. The use of magnesium sulfate has become more common over the years. Maternal diastolic blood pressure at admission to the hospital was significantly associated with perinatal mortality.

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